

About us

Libraria is a collective of researchers based in the social sciences who seek to bring about a more open, diverse, community-controlled scholarly communication system.

We are conducting a feasibility study for a cooperative of small, scholar-led open access publications in anthropology and adjacent fields. We are asking you, as someone who is connected to such a publication, to complete the following survey so as to help us better understand the opportunities for cooperation in this domain.

We will securely store the data collected with this survey until December 31, 2021. The data collected will be used in anonymized, aggregated form in public presentations of the study. We will never sell or share this data with any third parties.

At the end of the survey, you will be given the option to provide your name and contact information. This personally identifying information will be used in conjunction with the other data that you provide to facilitate conversations among participating publications.

If you would like to access, amend, or request deletion of the data that you provide after you have completed the survey, or if you have any other questions or concerns, please contact Kate Herman at kate@libraria.cc.

Having read the Privacy Notice on the previous page, do you agree to take part in this survey sent to you by Libraria?

Yes, I consent

No, I do not consent

Block 2

What potential benefits of cooperation with other open access publications interest you the most? Below, we've grouped some potential answers into broad categories. Please select all that apply; subsequent questions will allow you to get more specific within each of these categories.

Don't feel constrained by what's here! You can also offer your own ideas in the free response field.

- Knowledge sharing
- Labor sharing
- Cooperatively sourced funding
- Cooperatively owned tools and infrastructure
- If none of the above broad categories is applicable, please tell us what other benefits of cooperation interest you:

In terms of **knowledge sharing**, what interests you most?

- Knowledge sharing among all members of a cooperative
- Knowledge sharing within cohorts of similar publications

Other:

In terms of **labor sharing**, what interests you most?

- Web development and metrics support
- Copyediting, proofing, and other production support
- Discoverability and metadata support
- Preservation and archiving support
- Visibility and social media support
- Multilingual and translation support
- Other:

In terms of **cooperatively sourced funding**, what interests you most?

- Shared revenue model

Other:

In terms of **cooperatively owned tools and infrastructure**, what interests you most?

- Shared reviewer database
- Shared publishing platform
- Searchable portal of publications, with each on its own platform
- Other

Next steps

Would you be willing to participate in a virtual discussion with other participating publications about your publication's needs in these areas?

- Yes
- No

Wonderful! Please provide your name and email address and we will reach out to you to set up a convenient time.

Name

Email

Journal you represent

Do you consent to the use of your personal details and of the information provided above to explore the feasibility of a publishing cooperative?

- Yes, I consent
- No, I do not consent

What other open access publications in anthropology and adjacent fields should Libraria consider contacting to explore opportunities for cooperation?

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